

Thank you for your review and the constructive suggestions you shared with us. We have carefully taken into consideration your comments and revised our protocol consequently.

Firstly, in section 1.1 we decided to delete the option of downloading data through SPARQL query and opted to download OpenCitations data dump. The dump is the February 2023 version. The same goes for step 4 where we also had envisioned the possibility of retrieving data by means of SPARQL query, but eventually came down to agreeing with the reviewer that this is not an optimal solution. Instead, we decided to retrieve this information during the initial processing of OpenCitations Meta dump.

In section 2.1. we eventually realized it would be redundant to use both disciplines classification systems and we decided to only include ERIH-PLUS disciplines classification. Therefore, we will not need to map the disciplines in the end.

For section 2.3. we plan to look for options to retrieve missing information about countries other than from DOAJ. One option could be searching manually, if there are not too many publishers to look for. Or we can find other indexes or directories whose data can be accessible via download or API. In case none of these options is feasible, we plan to state clearly in the critique of the article that there is missing information for a small part of our data due to lack of information in our data sources.

Finally, as for your suggestion of a more comprehensive visualization we think our visualization outline is comprehensive for the sake of our research and we wonder if you could give a more specific critique or suggestion.